

Factors influencing the Photo-catalytic degradation of crystal violet with combustion synthesized $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$

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Abstract: $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ has been prepared by combustion method using Ferric nitrate, H_2MoO_4 and glycine as a raw materials. After calcination of obtained powder at 400 °C for 4 hrs characterized with XRD and SEM. From the XRD peaks we can say that the obtained catalyst is phase pure and does not contain any impurities and SEM studies revealed particle size in the μm region. The sample as prepared showed excellent photo catalytic activity for the degradation of crystal violet in presence of H_2O_2 either under visible light irradiation using 400 W metal halide lamp. Photo catalytic studies on 100 ml aqueous dye solutions with 100 mg of dispersed catalyst under visible light irradiation indicated degradation of 93% of 5ppm crystal violet in 70 min.

Keywords: $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$, Combustion synthesis, H_2O_2 , Crystal Violet, photo catalytic degradation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In several nations, including China, India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, the textile industry is one of the most well-known and developed sectors. However, it faces the problem of unplanned wastewater effluent generation. An excessive amount of water (120–280L) and a variety of colors are used to complete the wet fabric manufacturing process, which involves several phases like printing, dyeing, and finishing [1]. Synthetic dyes therefore exacerbate water contamination, and wastewater containing dyes is a basic environmental problem that significantly impedes sustainable development and so urgently needs appropriate treatment for dye removal due to growing water scarcity challenges [2-4].

Ion exchange techniques, adsorption, membrane separating technology, and electrochemical purification are some of the waste water refining technologies that have been developed to combat water resource pollution [5, 6]. Nevertheless, there are still challenges, including high energy consumption, secondary pollutants, low adsorption capability, and inactivity as soon as it arrives. Photo-induced catalytic degradation has recently attracted a lot of attention as a potential solution to this issue [7]. Compared to other energy sources, solar power has a number of benefits, including being economical, limitless, and eco-friendly.

Various metal oxides, including titanium dioxide (TiO_2), cerium oxide (CeO_2), zinc oxide (ZnO), zirconium oxide (ZrO_2), manganese oxide (MnO_2), and tin oxide (SnO_2), have been identified as practical materials for photo-catalysis [8, 9]. These oxides generate highly oxidizing photo-induced holes and are valued for their affordability, wide availability, low toxicity, eco-friendly, and stability across a broad pH range [10–13]. However, these metal oxides have relatively large band gap energies, limiting their photo-catalytic efficiency and insufficient mineralization. These shortcomings pose significant challenges when using these materials for photo-catalytic degradation [14, 15]. However, high electron and hole transportation rates are essential for the effective oxidative decomposition of dye molecules. Several limitations hinder the efficiency of photo-catalytic degradation, including a high recombination rate of electrons (e^-) and holes (h^+) [16, 17]. Consequently, pure metal

oxides exhibit relatively low photocatalytic performance. Research has focused on enhancing their efficiency by developing metal oxide nano composites, core-shell nano structures, rare-earth-doped metal oxides, and other advanced materials [18–20].

A broad range of Non TiO₂ photo responsive mixed metal oxides including have been produced for water treatment. Recent studies have identified iron compounds that are sensitive to beam of light having wave length ranges between 200 nm to 800 nm and exhibit a band gap of less than or equal to 2.9 eV, like Fe₂O₃ [21], ZnFe₂O₄ [22], LaFeO₃ [23], BiFeO₃ [24], Fe₂Mo₃O₁₂ [25-29], etc., have been created to effective uses for the degradation of different dyes in presence of light sources. Because of structural characteristics, non-toxicity, and efficacy towards the visible light spectrum, Ferric molybdate (Fe_xMo_yO_z) is widely recognized as an effective material for the degradation of waste water effluents under visible-light irradiation [30]. In this paper, the combustion synthesized Fe₂Mo₃O₁₂ catalyst was prepared and characterized using XRD and SEM to know structural, morphological, elemental, vibration and electrical structure. Crystal violet (CV) dye degradation was conducted with the help of solar radiation.

II. Experimental details:

(a) Synthesis of Catalyst:

Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O and MoO₃ of AR Quality were starting materials; 6.83g Fe(NO₃)₃ and 7.3004g H₂MoO₄ were added to 50 mL of water under constant stirring followed by the addition of 0.76149g of glycine. The precursor solution containing dispersed H₂MoO₄ was then heated on a hot plate at 110 °C until it became viscous with liberation of large amounts of brown fumes. The dried mass was then calcined at 400 °C for 4 hrs. The resultant powder was ground for homogeneity and used for phase identification.

(b) Characterization Techniques:

Phase purity of the calcined powder was investigated with X-ray diffractometer (PANalytical- X^{PERT} PRO, Japan), using nickel filtered Cu-K α radiation (λ = 1.54059 Å), with a scan rate of 2° min⁻¹. UV–visible diffuse reflectance spectrum (UVDRS) of the sample was obtained with the dry pressed disk samples using Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV-3600) between 200 to 800 nm range. Spectral grade BaSO₄ was taken as reference for the reflectance spectra. Micro structural investigation of the sample was performed on the powdered sample using SEM (JEOL-JSM-6610LV, Tokyo, Japan).

Photocatalytic activity:

Photo catalytic activity of Fe₂(MoO₄)₃ was evaluated in terms of degradation of crystal violet under visible light irradiation from 400 W metal halide lamp as a light source for irradiation. UV radiation below 350nm is eliminated by surrounding the sample with a water jacket, when sample solution irradiated in metal halide lamp. 100 mg of the catalyst powder was added into 100ml CV solution (5 mg/L) and the suspension was magnetically stirred for half an hour in dark to ensure adsorption/desorption equilibrium between photo-catalyst powder and dye. The suspension was then exposed to light emanating from the source; 5ml aliquot were pipetted at periodic time intervals and filtered through 0.45 micron Millipore filters to remove the suspended powder. Progress of decolorization was followed by recording the corresponding absorption spectrum. All the experiments were conducted under ambient conditions.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

XRD pattern of resultant powder obtained from the mixture of Ferric nitrate, H_2MoO_4 and glycine mixed in water and calcined at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is shown in Fig. 1. The observed peaks could be indexed to $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ of JCPDS File no 83-1701. Scanning electron microscopic study of the calcined powder is depicted in Fig. 2 from which it can be seen that the particle size is in μm region.

Figure 1. (a) XRD pattern and (b) SEM image of $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ photo-catalyst

Temporal variation of spectral changes of aqueous dye solution as a function of irradiation time for aqueous solution of CV, CV + H_2O_2 , and dye solution + H_2O_2 + $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ are shown in Fig. 2. From the intensity changes in respective spectral contours, it can be seen that the photo-degradation of dye solution alone showed 39 % degradation for 200 mins 2(a). In presence of H_2O_2 however, the dye solution showed 85.6 % degradation of CV for an irradiation of 200 mins 2(b). But in presence of both catalyst and H_2O_2 effected complete degradation takes place within 45 mins of irradiation time under the same conditions 2(c).

Fig. 2 Temporal variation of spectral changes for (a) aqueous CV solution, (b) CV solution + H_2O_2 and (c) dye solution + $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ + H_2O_2 as a function of irradiation time.

The above data indicates that combination of $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ + H_2O_2 is very effective in lowering the degradation time significantly compared to previous reports in literature.

Effect of H_2O_2 :

Fig. 3. Spectra relating to photo catalytic degradation of CV with (a) 8 μmole , (b) 10 μmole and (c) 12 μmole H_2O_2 , as a function of irradiation time.

Variations of spectral intensities for degradation of CV aqueous solution with 100 mg photo catalyst dispersed as a function of irradiation time are shown in Fig. 3 for 8, 10 and 12 μmole of H_2O_2 . From the figure, it can be seen that 12 μmole of H_2O_2 is optimum for the photo degradation of 100 ml aqueous solution of 5 ppm CV.

Effect of amount of catalyst:

Fig. 4 Spectra relating to photo-catalytic degradation of CV with (a) 50 mg, (b) 100 mg and (c) 150 mg photo-catalyst, as a function of irradiation time.

In order to study the effect due to amount of catalyst, each containing spectra relating to degradation of 100 ml aqueous solutions 5 ppm CV and 12 μmole H_2O_2 with 50, 100 and 150 mg of dispersed photo-catalyst as a function of irradiation time are recorded and shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen from the spectra that 100 mg of photo-catalyst is sufficient to effect complete in 45 min degradation.

Effect of Dye Concentration:

Fig. 5. Spectra relating to photo-catalytic degradation of CV with different initial concentrations of pollutant of (a) 5 ppm, (b) 10 ppm and (c) 15 ppm, as a function of irradiation time.

Intensity variations in spectral changes for degradation of 100 ml of aqueous solutions containing 5, 10 and 15 ppm CV with 12 $\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2$ and 100 mg of photo-catalyst each as a function of irradiation time are shown in Fig. 4.39. From the figure, it can be seen that as the dye concentration increases the degradation time also increases.

IV. CONCLUSION

$\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ prepared by combustion method showed a synergistic effect in the photo-catalytic degradation of crystal violet dye. The present study revealed that rapid degradation can be achieved in presence of H_2O_2 . The dye aqueous solutions of crystal violet showed complete bleaching in 45 min as compared to 90-360 min reported in literature. The rapid degradation occurred with 5 ppm of CV with 150 mg of $\text{Fe}_2\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{12}$ photo-catalyst and 12 $\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2$.

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